

Well	ExptType	Experiment	Sample	TargetType	Target	Status	Concentration	Supermix	CopiesPer20uLWell
A06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.5	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	30
B07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.57	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	11.4
C07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.63	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	12.6
D06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	14.3	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	286
D07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
F06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	5.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
F07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	5.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.1	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	22
G06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	6.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
G07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	6.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
H06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	7.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.3	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	26
H07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	7.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.8	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	36
A08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	8.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.73	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	14.6
A09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	8.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	9.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	20
B09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	9.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.74	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	14.8
C08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	10.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	10.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.8	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	36
D08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	11.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.63	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	12.6
D09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	11.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.6	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	12
E08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	12.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.1	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	22
E09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	12.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.2	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	24
F08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	13.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
F09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	13.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.7	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	34

TotalConfMax	TotalConfMin	PoissonConfMax	PoissonConfMin	Positives	Negatives	Ch1+Ch2+	Ch1+Ch2-	Ch1-Ch2+	Ch1-Ch2-	Linkage	AcceptedDroplets
				0	13803						13803
				0	14180						14180
		2.3	0.9	19	15020						15039
				7161	1465						8626
		1.1	0.24	7	14521						14528
		1.17	0.28	8	15050						15058
		16.4	12.3	192	15672						15864
				186	15041						15227
				0	14805						14805
				0	15592						15592
				0	15244						15244
		1.8	0.6	15	16063						16078
				0	15527						15527
				0	15106						15106
		2.1	0.8	18	15757						15775
		2.6	1.2	25	16419						16444
		1.28	0.36	10	16146						16156
				0	16979						16979
		1.7	0.6	14	16026						16040
		1.27	0.38	11	17458						17469
				0	16863						16863
		2.6	1.2	23	15031						15054
		1.13	0.3	9	16900						16909
		1.13	0.27	8	15662						15670
		1.8	0.6	15	15744						15759
		1.8	0.7	17	17108						17125
				17	16008						16025
		2.4	1.1	24	17073						17097

PoissonFractionalAbundanceMin	ReferenceAssayNumber	TargetAssayNumber	Threshold	MeanAmplitudeofPositives	MeanAmplitudeofNegatives
	1	1	0	0	4463.7
	1	1	0	0	3090
	1	1	6610	8573.4	5893
	1	1	3330	5682.6	1640.4
	1	1	7162	11036	5784.9
	1	1	6895	8600.7	5693.4
	1	1	8355	25099	4658.1
	1	1	7452	25987	4280
	1	1	0	0	4566.2
	1	1	0	0	4223.8
	1	1	0	0	5132.4
	1	1	5642	7965.1	4853.8
	1	1	0	0	5232.6
	1	1	0	0	4907.9
	1	1	6070	8228.5	5070.7
	1	1	5318	5996.3	4700
	1	1	5182	8387.2	4493.2
	1	1	0	0	4276
	1	1	4898	8963.5	4381.8
	1	1	4896	15929	4151.5
	1	1	0	0	4695.2
	1	1	5066	5770.3	4489.8
	1	1	5733	9214.2	4804.9
	1	1	5234	12640	4585.8
	1	1	5260	12495	4520.6
	1	1	5030	11590	4289.1
	1	1	5237	8842.6	4571.3
	1	1	5073	9248.7	4379.8

MeanAmplitudeTotal	ExperimentComments	MergedWells	TotalConfMax68	TotalConfMin68	PoissonConfMax68	PoissonConfMin68
4463.7	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
3090	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5896.3	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.85	1.17
4996.1	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5787.4	Absolute Quantification Experiment				0.81	0.38
5695	Absolute Quantification Experiment				0.87	0.43
4905.5	Absolute Quantification Experiment				15.4	13.3
4545.2	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4566.2	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4223.8	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5132.4	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4856.7	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.41	0.84
5232.6	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4907.9	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5074.3	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.69	1.05
4702	Absolute Quantification Experiment				2.17	1.46
4495.6	Absolute Quantification Experiment				0.98	0.52
4276	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4385.8	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.33	0.78
4158.9	Absolute Quantification Experiment				0.99	0.54
4695.2	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4491.8	Absolute Quantification Experiment				2.2	1.45
4807.3	Absolute Quantification Experiment				0.86	0.44
4589.9	Absolute Quantification Experiment				0.84	0.41
4528.2	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.44	0.86
4296.4	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.48	0.91
4575.8	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4386.6	Absolute Quantification Experiment				2.01	1.34

